

Teachers' Self-efficacy and Use of Information Resources by Secondary School Teachers in Selected Secondary Schools in Ijebu Ode Local Government, Ogun State

Temitope A. Osisanwo (PhD)

Department of Library and Information Science, Tai Solarin University of Education, Nigeria
osisanwota@tasued.edu.ng

Mobolanle O. Sodipe (CLN, FAIMP)

Gbenga Daniel Library, Tai Solarin University of Education, Nigeria
sodipemo@tasued.edu.ng
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Abstract

The study investigated the teacher's self-efficacy and use of information resources by secondary school teachers in selected secondary schools. The study adopted a descriptive survey research design. The population of this study comprised of the 238 teachers in the five selected secondary schools in Ijebu-Ode Local Government. Total enumeration was used to capture all the 238 teachers in the five selected secondary schools in Ijebu ode. A questionnaire designed by the researcher was used for data collection. 238 copies of questionnaire were administered while 201 was retrieved and used for data analysis. The findings revealed that there is low level of self-efficacy among teachers, the major information resources that are available to teachers are reference books, online resources and textbooks, the major problems affecting the use of information resources by teachers are lack of update and current resource. Government should provide the schools management with up-to-date information resources to assist teachers in accessing recent and up to date information that will assist them to improve the quality of their academic and research work. The study therefore recommends that government should provide the schools management with more and up to date information resources to assist teachers in accessing recent and up to date information.

Keywords: Information resources, Secondary school, Teachers' self-efficacy, Use

Introduction

Information resources can be described to include any information channel or a medium through which information is made available or accessible to information seekers both in print and electronic format. The information resource could also be hardware/software intended for the storage, transmission and use of information as well as the digital content files that may be stored, transmitted, or used. They include e-mail, local databases, and externally accessed databases, CD-ROM or other digitised information. In the new technological environment, academic members of the school use an increasing array of information resources, including online databases, OPACs, e-conference materials, e-mail, full-text databases, e-books, and scholarly websites (Jirojwong & Wallin, 2010, p. 20-21). The use of these resources is important to both academic and managerial activities because of its ability to provide users with timely, easy-to-access, and, up-to-date information

Self-efficacy is general view of oneself across various sets of specific domains and perceptions based on self-knowledge and evaluation of values formed through experiences in relation to one's environment (Eccles, 2015, p. 20-22). It is the perception that each one has about oneself, formed from experiences and relationships with the environment. It is a component of human personality development that has its own nature and peculiarity (Sayid, 2011, p. 377-392) where significant teachers play an important role. Academic Self-efficacy is referred to as a teachers' self-evaluation regarding specific academic domains or abilities (Trautwein, 2016, p. 81-87).

Teachers' self-efficacy is the set of knowledge and attitudes that teachers have about themselves - the perceptions that the individual assigns to him or herself and characteristics or attributes that teachers use to describe one self. It is understood to be fundamentally a descriptive assessment that has a cognitive expression. It is the reflection of teacher's personal beliefs in his own capacity to achieve educational duties at projected levels.

Statement of the problem

The use of information resources is important to academic staffs in our secondary schools because of its ability to provide users with timely, easy to access and up-to-date information on various topics as teachers prepare lesson notes and also prepare pupils for final and certificate exams. But the extent of use of these information resources appears abysmally low. The low level of usage of these resources could be as a result of level of teachers' self-efficacy or various degrees of challenges faced by teachers while trying to use the information resources. In the light of the above, this study tends to investigate the teacher's self-efficacy and use of information resources among secondary school teachers in selected secondary schools in Ijebu-Ode in Ogun state.

Research questions

The research questions of the study are as follows:

- (i) What is the level of self-efficacy among teachers in selected secondary schools in Ijebu-Ode Local Government, Ogun State?
- (ii) What are the available information resources to teachers in selected secondary schools in Ijebu-Ode Local Government, Ogun State?
- (iii) What are the various information resources used by teachers in selected secondary schools in Ijebu-Ode Local Government, Ogun State?
- (iv) What are the problems affecting the use of information resources by teachers in selected secondary schools in Ijebu-Ode Local Government, Ogun State?

Research hypothesis

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between teachers' self-efficacy and use of information resources among teachers

Literature review

Concept of information resources

Information resources, according to Ku (2018) refer to those materials that require computer access, whether through microcomputer, mainframe, or other types of computers, and that may either be locally mounted or accessed remotely via the Internet (p. 253). 'Information resources', as a term, is usually interchangeably used with such other terms as "Information resources", "Virtual resources", "Online resources", and "Digital resources". Information resources have been useful to school community both in the developed and the developing nations of the world. The School of Kansas Information Service (2015) defines information resources to include any hardware/software intended for the storage, transmission and use of information as well as the digital content files that may be stored, transmitted, or used with hardware/software. These include e-mail, voice systems, local databases, and externally accessed databases, among others.

The use of these resources is vital for academic and research activities because of its ability to provide users with timely, easy to access and, up-to-date information. For instance, ScienceDirect which is a database that houses e-books adequately supports researches in the fields of natural science, medicine, engineering, food science and social studies, enabling users to access up-to-date information in the sciences. However, the sudden upsurge of these resources is a resultant effect of a number of changes brought about by the development of cutting-edge and emerging information technology. The evolution of Information technology has globally transformed the landscape of the library and information practice by provoking a shift in roles, resources, and services provided by library and information professionals.

Information resources from varying sources are now available in enormous quantity. Kumar (2017) stated that the explosive growth of Information resources which gives access to reliable and up-to-date information has helped educational institutions to stay at the forefront of this changing

world and for research to be reliable; it must be based on up-to-date and reliable information. Information resources have become essential for the school studies and are very popular to most of the teacher because they can provide a number of advantages over traditional print based sources (p. 3-5)

Ekhaguere et al. (2015) asserted that limited access to up-to-date journals and books in the different disciplines had been a great challenge to teacher and researchers until the development of Internet. To him, the Internet is the vista to retrieving up-to-date information. The research and other academic activities that go on in the universities involves collating and processing of data and a good research work depends greatly on a teacher's skill in retrieving current and relevant information. (p. 388-389). With the availability of Information resources, research is no longer complicated. This is due to the fact that most of the documents to be consulted for research are available in electronic formats like the Internet, online database, OPACs, electronic journals, electronic books, etc. The use of Information resources encourages collaboration among teacher and researchers.

Fakolujo (2015) reported that “electronic mail (e-mail) over the Internet enables one to overcome many barriers to communicate due to geographic distance such as time, costs and language” (p. 233-250). More so, virtual study or research teams can also be formed by the teacher to link a variety of other teacher to enable them to contribute their skills towards a particular project. Bamiro et al. (2015) posited that the electronic mail (e-mail) mode of communication provided by the Internet helps in sending and receiving messages at a very fast and cheap rate (p. 17-20). Ureigho et al. (2016) explained that besides the use of Internet for e-mail, one can listen to international radio stations on research and education on the Internet (p. 255-257). Furthermore, teacher can read books and other materials, speak to press round the globe and read national dailies of other countries electronically.

Concept of self-efficacy

Bandura (2017) defines self-efficacy as the ‘beliefs in one’s capabilities to organize and execute the courses of action required to produce given attainments. According to him, the level of self-efficacy will determine whether a task will be initiated and completed (p. 821-836). A learner with high self-efficacy will be motivated to put in more effort, persist longer and complete a given task. As a result, self-efficacy and motivation are perceived to have a bidirectional relationship. According to researchers (Guthrie & Wigfield, 2010; Grabe & Stoller, 2012), self-efficacy influences motivation, promotes strategy use and increases learner autonomy. Similarly, reading motivation promotes frequent reading, which contributes to the use of appropriate reading strategies and high self-efficacy (Guthrie & Wigfield, 2010). Appropriate and well-orchestrated strategy use in reading and learning increases self-efficacy and motivation, and also contributes to a high level of comprehension in reading, which may lead to better academic performance. Self-efficacy has been perceived to emanate from several sources.

Self-efficacy is best conceived as a differentiated set of self-beliefs specific to different areas of functioning (social self-efficacy, academic self-efficacy); and is therefore considered a domain-specific concept as no person can feel competent at all tasks (Valentine et al., 2015). Self-efficacy is the measure of one’s competences to complete tasks and reach goals (Ormrod, 2016). It influences every aspect of human endeavours. It could be referred to as a person’s belief in his or her ability to successfully accomplish a specific task. It also refers to beliefs about one’s capabilities to learn or perform behaviours at designated levels. Much research shows that self-efficacy influences academic motivation, learning and achievement (Schunk, 2018).

Thus, teachers’ self-efficacy is operationally defined as a teacher’s belief for his/her own capabilities that he/ she can accomplish a given task and can produce desired outcomes. These beliefs are developed on the basis of positive or negative past experiences, by observing other teachers, teachers or role models who are in quite similar situations or are similar in abilities and

skills and perform well or poor, by receiving positive or negative feedback from others and by their positive and negative emotional states.

Moreover, Bandura et al. (2019) investigated the central role played by perceived self-regulatory efficacy of 412 Italian teachers in their academic development and functioning over three time periods. Longitudinal findings indicated that there was a decline in self-regulatory efficacy from junior to senior high school but those who experienced the lowest decline in self-regulatory efficacy had the higher grades and the greater chance of remaining in school. In sum, high perceived self-regulatory efficacy contributed positively to junior high grades. Social self-efficacy refers to a willingness to initiate behaviour in social situations. The abilities to establish friendships, form sustainable peer relationships, receive positive peer praise, be socially acceptable, and behave in a prosocial manner at school are all important tasks for success at school and have been found to be directly related to academic performance (Patrick et al., 2017).

Self-efficacy beliefs also contribute to performance since they influence thought processes, motivation, and behaviour. Fluctuations in performance may be explained by fluctuations in self-efficacy. For example, varying beliefs in self-efficacy may alter task outcome, whether it involves two similarly-skilled teachers or the same person in two different situations. Teachers high in self-efficacy attempt challenging tasks more often, persist longer at them, and exert more effort. If there are failures, highly efficacious teachers attribute it to a lack of effort or an adverse environment. When they succeed, they credit their achievement to their abilities. The perception that their abilities caused the achievement affects the outcome rather than their actual abilities. Conversely, teachers with high self-efficacy frequently persevere despite difficult tasks or challenging odds and often succeed because perseverance usually results in a successful outcome. Numerous studies link self-efficacy to academic performance. For example, in seventh grade Science and English classes, self-efficacy was positively related to cognitive engagement and academic performance. Self-efficacy, self-regulated learning, and test anxiety also were found to be the best performance predictors (Chemers et al., 2011).

Albert Bandura defined self-efficacy as a teacher's belief that he or she will be able to accomplish a specific task. He believed that an essential component to accomplishing something is our confidence that we can. Bandura referred to self-efficacy as the mind's self-regulatory function; it tells us when to try and when to stop. If you do not believe something is possible, you are less likely to attempt the task and more likely to give up early if you do. Self-efficacy drives your motivation; just as you have different degrees of motivation depending on the task, so also do you have different levels of self-efficacy. You may have high self-efficacy when it comes to your job because you have done it for a long time. You may have low self-efficacy in regards to school because you struggled to make passing grades. The level of self-efficacy you have when you begin a task has a great deal to do with whether you will successfully complete it.

Downs (2015) conducted a study on the influence of self-efficacy on Native American high school teachers' academic performance. The finding revealed that self-efficacy significantly and positively correlated with academic performance. Schallert (2016) found in his study that self-efficacy significantly predicted teachers' academic performance in sciences. Pajares (2015) and Zimmerman (2010) found in their various studies that self-efficacy significantly influenced teachers' academic performance. Klassen et al. (2018) found that academic self-efficacy was a strong predictor of academic performance. However, contrary findings have been reported by a few empirical studies. For instance, Saunders et al. (2015) and Loo and Choy (2013) found that self-efficacy had small positive effect on academic performance. Self-efficacy also indirectly affects perseverance. Although past achievement raises self-efficacy, it is teacher interpretation of past successes and failures that may be responsible for subsequent success. Perceived self-efficacy predicts future achievement better than past performance (Jeffreys, 2018).

Use of information resources by teachers

Teacher especially, those in the universities use the Information resources for various academic purposes. These purposes include; doing class assignments, writing term papers, augmenting class works, retrieving current literature for studies, following blog discussions on subject area of interest, searching for scholarship opportunities, searching for internship placement and for research purposes. Considering the fact that universities are institutions of higher learning where studies of various degrees take place and similarly, research requires the use of current and up-to-date literatures, it then becomes very necessary that EIRs are greatly used by the teacher in the universities. According to Oyegade (2010) the Internet, which is an electronic information resource is regarded as the best Channel for information retrieval for teacher research work because it is the gateway to the globe. He opined that it allows different groups of people especially teacher and researchers to create channels of communication and self-expression.

Rosen and Castro (2012) described the school teacher as being thirsty for information, but not bringing a cup to drink. Water is everywhere but no knowledge of how to drink. Without real information skills, teacher searching for knowledge might as well be chasing a mirage in the desert. Although the Information resources has been gaining popularity on school campuses, and is highly desirable in that it leads to increased productivity of work, learning, teaching and research, school teacher, especially those in developing nations are yet to achieve optimal utilisation of these resources. The importance and wide-ranging scope of information resources for general communication, information retrieval and research activities in tertiary educational institutions for academic activities is acknowledged worldwide. Literature also show that a number of relevant studies have been carried out on the use of e-resources by teacher worldwide. General user opinion towards the use of information resources, in particular CD-ROM, has been positive, with teacher enjoying using these sources and finding relatively few problems while using them (Ray and Day, 2018).

Ojo and Akande (2015) in a survey of 350 respondents examined teacher access, usage and awareness of Information resources at the School College Hospital (UCH) Ibadan, Nigeria. The study revealed that the level of usage of the information resources by teacher for academic activities is not high. A major problem however identified is lack of information retrieval skills for exploiting information resources, thus making the level of usage of resources by teachers very low. The study conducted by Ojedokun (2011) on “Internet access and usage by the teacher of Botswana”, revealed that though Internet resources were provided and made accessible, they were under-utilised. Quite a number of studies exist with the result that school libraries in Nigeria are generally poorly utilised.

Methodology

The descriptive survey research design was adopted for this study. The population of this study comprised of the 238 teachers in the five selected secondary schools in Ijebu-Ode Local Government, Ogun State. Descriptive statistics such as frequency counts, percentage, mean and standard deviation was used to analyse the research questions while Pearson correlation was used to analyse the hypothesis.

Table 1: Distribution of population

S/N	Secondary Schools	Year of Establishment	Total Number of Teachers
1	Adeola Odutola College Ijebu ode	1964	57
2	Moslem Comprehensive High School, Ijebu ode	1972	36
3	Ijebu-Ode Grammar School, Ijebu ode	1913	54
4	Ijebu Muslim College, Ijebu ode	1950	52
5	Our Lady of Apostle Secondary School, Ijebu ode	1954	39
	Total		238

Results

Table 2: Demographic information of respondents

DEMOGRAPHIC FEATURES	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Gender		
Male	69	34.5
Female	131	65.5
Religion		
Christianity	114	57
Muslim	86	43
Others	-	-
Marital status		
Single	31	15.5
Married	159	79.5
Divorce	10	5.0
TOTAL	201	100%

Table 2 shows the demographic characteristics of the respondents. The result showed that 69 (34.5%) of the respondents were male while 131 (65.5%) of the respondents were female, which implies that the female respondents are more than the male respondents that took part in the study. Based on their religion, it could be depicted that 114 (57%) of the respondents that participated in the study were Christians, 86 (43%) of the respondents were Muslims, while nobody indicated any other religion. However, based on their marital status, 31 (15.5%) of the respondents were single, 159 (79.5%) were married while 10 (5.0%) of the respondents were divorce.

Research question 1: What is the level of teachers' self-efficacy among teachers in selected secondary schools in Ijebu-Ode Local Government, Ogun State?

Table 3: Level of teachers' self-efficacy

Teachers' self-efficacy	Mean	Std. Dev.	Remarks
I can effectively motivate students who show low interest in schoolwork?	2.98	1.59	Significant
I am capable of improving students' memory of what they have been taught in previous lessons?	2.98	1.55	Significant
I can effectively do a lot to keep students on task on difficult assignments?	2.96	1.009	Significant
I can influence the decisions that are made in the school?	2.86	1.226	Significant
I can effectively put in my best to get students to trust teachers?	2.86	1.57	Significant
I am capable of helping other teachers with their teaching skills?	2.81	1.153	Significant
I can do a lot to enhance collaboration between teachers and the administration to make the school run effectively?	2.76	1.267	Significant
I can put in my best to reduce school dropout?	2.73	1.277	Significant
I can do a lot to control disruptive behaviour in the classroom?	2.70	.667	Significant
I can do a lot to prevent problem behaviour on the school grounds?	2.69	1.094	Significant
I can do a lot to get through to the most difficult students?	2.69	.920	Significant
I can promote learning when there is lack of support from the home?	2.67	.539	Significant
I can be of help to reduce school absenteeism?	2.64	.549	Significant
I can be of help to get students to believe they can do well in schoolwork?	2.49	.504	Non-Significant
I can get the instructional materials and equipment needed for teaching activities?	2.48	.648	Non-Significant
I can influence the class sizes in my school?	2.43	.496	Non-Significant
I can get children to do their homework when necessary?	2.41	.784	Non-Significant
I can get children to follow classroom rules and regulations?	2.28	.452	Non-Significant
I can easily get students to work together as a team?	2.00	.000	Non-Significant
I can overcome the influence of adverse community conditions	1.97	.381	Non-Significant

on students' learning?			
I can easily and freely express my views on important school matters?	1.74	.761	Non-Significant
I can do a lot to make the school a safe place?	1.60	.251	Non-Significant
I can effectively make students enjoy coming to school regularly?	1.47	.021	Non-Significant
GRAND MEAN	2.49		Non-significant

Decision: it has been adjudged that means score of $X=2.50$ and above is significant.

Result in Table 5 showed the level of self-efficacy among teachers in selected secondary schools. Test of norm was conducted to test the level of self-efficacy among teachers and the results showed that mean score of 2.50 and above is significant. The grand mean for the level of self-efficacy is ($\bar{x}= 2.49$) is an indication that there is low level of self-efficacy among teachers in selected secondary schools in Ijebu-Ode Local Government, Ogun State.

Research question 2: What are the information resources available to the teachers in selected secondary schools in Ijebu-Ode Local Government, Ogun State?

Table 4: Information resources available to teachers

Information Resources	Available	Not Available
Internet facilities and online resources	150(75%)	50(25%)
Textbooks	144(72%)	56(28%)
Journals	140(70%)	60(30%)
Newspaper/Magazine	120(60%)	80(40%)
Conference Proceedings/Papers	111(55.5%)	89(44.5%)
Dissertation/Thesis/Projects	110(55%)	90(45%)
Reference books	105(52.5%)	95(47.5%)
Map/Charts/Diagrams	104(52%)	96(48%)
Library Catalogue	92(46%)	108(54%)
Online Public Access Catalogue (OPAC)	91(45.5%)	109(54.5%)
Indexes and Abstracts	74(37%)	126(63%)
Monographs	50(25%)	150(75%)
Total	201	100%

The result in table 4 revealed that the major information resources that are available to teachers are reference books, internet facilities and online resources, textbooks, dissertation/thesis/projects, journals, conference proceedings/papers and newspapers/magazines.

Research question 3: What are the various information resources used by teachers in selected secondary schools in Ijebu-Ode Local Government, Ogun State?

Table 5: Various information resources used by teachers

Information Resources	Highly Utilised	Utilised	Not Utilised
Internet facilities and online resources	160(80%)	20(10%)	-
Textbooks	140(70%)	30(15%)	30(15%)
Journals	136(68%)	32(16%)	32(16%)
Newspaper/Magazine	130(65%)	36(18%)	34(17%)
Conference Proceedings/Papers	120(60%)	40(20%)	40(20%)
Dissertation/Thesis/Projects	116(58%)	44(22%)	40(20%)
Reference books	112(56%)	48(24%)	40(20%)
Map/Charts/Diagrams	90(45%)	82(41%)	28(14%)
Library Catalogue	92(46%)	54(27%)	54(27%)
Online Public Access Catalogue (OPAC)	54(27%)	48(24%)	98(49%)
Indexes and Abstracts	52(26%)	84(42%)	64(32%)
Monographs	24(12%)	54(27%)	122(61%)

The result in Table 5 revealed that the information resources mostly used by secondary school teachers are internet facilities, online resources, textbooks journals, newspapers/magazines, conference proceedings/papers, dissertation/theses/projects and reference books.

Research question 4: What are the problems affecting the use of information resources by teachers in selected secondary schools in Ijebu-Ode Local Government, Ogun State?

Table 6: Problems affecting the use of information resources by teachers

Problems	YES	NO
Slow connection speed	159(73.5%)	41(15%)
Constant power outage	170(56%)	30(7%)
Lack of update and current resource	167(56%)	33(12%)
Inadequate search skill	167(54.5%)	33(15%)
Lack of adequate information resources	167(51%)	33(12.5%)
Inadequate loaning period	145(51%)	53(23.5%)
Inadequate library services	137(47.5%)	64(13.5%)
Inadequate library space	170(44%)	30(7.5%)
Inadequate library use skills	140(40%)	60(18%)
Lack of effective information retrieval skills	30(5%)	170(38%)

The result in Table 6 revealed that the major problems affecting the use of information resources by teachers are slow connection speed, constant power outage, lack of update and current resource, inadequate search skill and lack of adequate information resources.

Research Hypothesis: There is no significant relationship between self-efficacy and use of information resources among teachers

Table 7: Pearson correlation analysis of research hypothesis

		Self-efficacy	Use of information resources
Self-efficacy	Pearson Correlation	1	.260
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.070
	N	201	201
Use of Information Resources	Pearson Correlation	.260	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.070	
	N	201	201

Table 7 presents the relationship between self-efficacy and use of information resources among teachers. The table shows that a negative relationship exists between self-efficacy and use of information resources ($r = .260$). The relationship between the two variables is however revealed to be non-significant ($p > .05$). Thus, null hypothesis was accepted. Hence, there is no significant relationship between self-efficacy and use of information resources among teachers, which implies that teachers' low self-efficacy affects the use of information resources.

Discussion of findings

The study revealed a low level of teachers' self-efficacy among teachers in selected secondary schools. The result is not in line with the findings of Hanan (2016) who reported that high mean scores were recorded for items response in relation to self-efficacy among teachers. The study also revealed that the major information resources that are available to teachers are reference books, internet facilities and online resources, textbooks, dissertation/ thesis/projects, journals, conference proceedings/papers and newspapers/magazines. This is in line with the study of Ekhaguere et al. (2015) who asserted that with the availability of information resources, research is no longer complicated. This is due to the fact that most of the documents to be consulted for research are available in electronic formats like the Internet, online database, OPACs, electronic journals, electronic books, etc. The use of Information resources encourages collaboration among teacher and researchers. The findings showed that the majorly available information resources to teachers are internet, textbooks, journals, term papers, among others. Magara (2012) opined that the emergence of the World Wide Web (WWW) enhance scholarly communication and a rise in computational science. Presently, many teachers rely on the web for their assignments, term papers, research and communication with their teachers. Teachers through the web also exchange ideas and information which can help their academic activities.

The findings further revealed that the information resources mostly used by secondary school teachers are internet facilities, online resources, textbooks journals, newspapers/magazines, conference proceedings / papers, dissertation / theses / projects and reference books. This result is not in line with the finding of Emerole and Ogugua (2017) that showed that there is low patronage of information resources as many users have not fully realised the potentials of the library in this information age.

The findings also showed that the major problems affecting the use of information resources by teachers are slow connection speed, constant power outage, lack of update and current resource, inadequate search skill and lack of adequate information resources. This is in line with the study of Ojo and Akande (2015) who revealed that the problems affecting the use of information resources by teachers are lack of information retrieval skills for exploiting information resources, thus making the level of usage of resources by teachers very low. Also, Grafstein (2012) revealed that the complexity of information resources which requires that one possesses computer and searching skills may pose a great challenge to its effective utilisation by teacher if they lack the skill required for its usage. Furthermore, research hypothesis revealed that there is no significant relationship between self-efficacy and use of information resources among teachers.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, it was concluded that the major information resources that are available and mostly used by teachers are reference books, internet facilities and online resources, textbooks, dissertation / thesis / projects, journals, conference proceedings/papers and newspapers/magazines. Teachers' ability to locate and access information; evaluate reliability of information; find the needed information; organise, analyse, interpret and evaluate information enhances effective use of information resources.

Recommendations

Based on the study's findings, the following are recommended:

- i. Government through the Ministry of Education should provide schools management with up-to-date information resources to assist teachers in Ijebu-Ode Local Government to improve the quality of their academic and research work.
- ii. There is the need for the government to regularly organise training and retraining programmes that can assist the teachers in Ijebu-Ode Local Government to improve their level of self-efficacy which will in turn further improve the teaching and learning activities in our secondary schools.
- iii. Schools in Ijebu-Ode Local Government should be provided with adequate supply of power that will make academic activities to be smoothly run. Government should also provide adequate funds for capital projects in secondary schools such as ICT centres where students and teachers can have free access and use information resources in both electronic and print formats.
- iv. Adequate internet facilities should be provided in secondary schools to ameliorate the issue of slow connection speed.

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